

Toward a General Graph-Based Abstraction Approach for Urban Trajectory Generation

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Abstract—Urban mobility data is important for urban analytics and transportation modeling, but real-world trajectory datasets are often limited by privacy constraints, restricted access, and missing or unreliable observations. In this paper, we propose a graph-based abstraction method for generating synthetic pedestrian trajectories from raw GPS data. The approach first clusters trajectory points into spatial regions, then builds a directed weighted mobility network from transitions between clusters. New trajectories are generated through a biased random walk on this network and mapped onto the road network using a routing engine to obtain geographically plausible routes. This abstraction also helps mitigate noise and incompleteness in the original data by reconstructing plausible movement patterns from aggregated spatial structure. We evaluate the method on two trajectory datasets from the Paris area and compare clustering techniques using heatmap-based spatial metrics. Our results show that agglomerative clustering provides a more suitable graph structure than DBSCAN for this generation task. Graph connectivity and compactness, shaped by spatial abstraction, play a key role in the quality of the generated data.

Index Terms—Trajectory generation, clustering, spatial graph

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of machine learning and deep learning has driven demand for large, high-quality datasets. Such data are essential for tasks including urban analytics, transportation modeling, simulation, and benchmarking. In practice, however, real-world human mobility datasets are often difficult to access, limited in scope, or strongly restricted due to privacy concerns. Even when available, they may contain missing observations, irregular sampling, or other forms of noise, which can reduce their utility for downstream analysis. For these reasons, synthetic trajectory generation is essential for expanding data availability while reducing reliance on sensitive individual records.

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In this paper, we propose a graph-based abstraction methodology for generating synthetic pedestrian trajectories. The core idea is to transform raw GPS trajectories into a discrete representation of movement across spatial regions, using clustering and graph representations. First, trajectory points are clustered to define representative spatial locations. Next, transitions between these locations are used to construct a directed weighted mobility graph. Synthetic trajectories are then generated by sampling paths on this graph through a biased random walk and finally projecting them back onto the road network using a routing engine. This pipeline combines data-driven mobility structure with infrastructure-aware path reconstruction, producing trajectories that are geographically plausible while remaining less tied to individual original traces. A central aspect of this approach is the role of spatial abstraction. The clustering step determines the granularity of the mobility representation: finer clustering preserves more local details, whereas coarser clustering yields a more compact and generalized view of the urban space. This abstraction is also useful when the original data are partial, sparse, or noisy, as grouping nearby observations into spatial regions can reduce the effect of irregular sampling and missing or imprecise GPS points, while still preserving the main movement structure. The choice of clustering granularity directly affects the topology of the mobility graph and, consequently, the properties of the generated trajectories. Studying this effect is important both from a modeling perspective, because graph structure influences the random walk process, and from a data generation perspective, because abstraction may help balance fidelity, robustness, and generalization.

To evaluate our approach, we compare different clustering strategies, such as Agglomerative [1] and DBSCAN [2], and analyze how clustering granularity affects the quality of the generated trajectories using spatial distribution metrics computed over density heatmaps. The evaluation is done on two pedestrian trajectory datasets from the Paris area with complementary characteristics. The first is a high-quality, consent-grounded dataset collected by a private company through a

dedicated mobile application, covering a single month of activity with rich individual detail but limited temporal and spatial scope. The second is a publicly available dataset derived from GPS traces voluntarily shared through OpenStreetMap (OSM), covering multiple years of mobility in major urban environments, including Paris, and enriched with semantic layers such as stops, points of interest, inferred transportation modes, and weather conditions.

Finally, the main contributions of this paper are:

- we present a modular pipeline for synthetic pedestrian trajectory generation based on spatial clustering, graph abstraction, random-walk sampling, and routing.
- we provide an empirical analysis, using a combination of two datasets, of how the choice of clustering method and clustering scale influences the fidelity of the generated trajectories with respect to the original spatial distribution.
- we show how the structural properties of the induced mobility graph, such as connectivity, density, and fragmentation, influence random-walk-based generation and overall data quality.

Our results show that agglomerative clustering provides a more suitable graph structure than DBSCAN for this generation task, and that the degree of spatial abstraction has a clear impact on the quality of the generated data. Furthermore, our approach offers greater interpretability compared to many recent black-box methods in the literature.

II. RELATED WORK

The generation of realistic trajectory data has received significant attention in mobility data management, urban analytics, and transportation modeling. Synthetic trajectories are used to overcome limitations of real mobility datasets, including privacy constraints, incomplete coverage, and the need for controlled experimentation. Existing approaches can be broadly grouped into simulation-based models, learning-based generative methods, and graph-based mobility models.

Early work on synthetic mobility generation relied primarily on simulation models designed to reproduce realistic movement patterns. Classical approaches include mobility models which simulate movement in spatial environments according to predefined rules like the well-known traffic simulator SUMO [3]. While these models are useful for network simulations, they often fail to capture the structural constraints and behavioral patterns observed in real-world urban mobility.

More recent approaches generate trajectories by learning patterns directly from real data, employing probabilistic models or deep generative models from historical trajectory datasets [4]. Generative approaches based on recurrent neural networks, variational autoencoders, or generative adversarial networks have been proposed to synthesize realistic trajectories while preserving statistical properties of the original data [5]. However, these models typically require large training datasets.

Recent works have exploited graph representations to model mobility flows and movement patterns. Transitions between

locations can be modeled as a Markov process over a graph derived from historical trajectories [6]. Random walk processes over such graphs have been used to simulate plausible mobility sequences while preserving the structural properties of the observed movement network. These approaches provide an effective way to generate synthetic trajectories that remain consistent with observed transition patterns between locations as for example in [7].

Trajectory clustering and abstraction techniques are often used to reduce the complexity of large trajectory datasets and to extract representative movement patterns. Hierarchical and density-based clustering methods have been widely used to identify meaningful spatial regions from trajectory datasets and they can then be used as higher-level units for modeling mobility patterns.

When synthetic trajectories are generated at an abstract level, it is often necessary to reconstruct realistic paths that follow the road network. Map-matching [8] and routing algorithms are commonly used for this purpose. Routing engines such as GraphHopper [9] compute feasible paths between spatial locations based on the underlying road network, ensuring that generated trajectories remain physically plausible. This approach allows synthetic mobility models to combine statistical mobility patterns with realistic transportation infrastructure constraints.

In this work, we combine ideas from trajectory clustering, graph-based mobility modeling, and road-network routing to generate realistic pedestrian trajectories, filling a gap in the current literature.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our trajectory generation pipeline is depicted in Figure 1, and consists of three main stages: spatial abstraction through clustering, mobility network construction, and synthetic trajectory generation through random-walk sampling and routing.

A. Spatial abstraction by clustering

Let us suppose we have a real trajectory dataset D , where each trajectory is represented as an ordered sequence of GPS points. Since raw trajectories tend to be continuous and highly irregular in space, we first transform them into a discrete representation by grouping nearby points into spatial clusters. This step reduces noise, abstracts movement patterns, and defines a finite set of locations that can be used as the nodes of a mobility graph. Formally, let $c(\cdot)$ denote a clustering function. Given the set of all trajectory points in D , the clustering step assigns each point to a cluster, thereby producing a set of representative spatial regions C :

$$C = c(D) \quad (1)$$

This abstraction is important for two reasons. First, it compresses the original trajectories into sequences of semantically meaningful spatial units. Second, it introduces a controllable level of generalization: by varying the clustering parameters (e.g., the number of clusters), we can obtain either finer or coarser representations of the same mobility space.

Fig. 1: The overall methodology of our approach for trajectory generation

B. Mobility network construction

Once the clusters have been identified, we construct a directed weighted graph that captures the transition structure observed in the original trajectories, by using a function $net(\cdot)$:

$$G(V, E, W) = net(C) \quad (2)$$

where V is the set of cluster nodes, and each node $v \in V$ corresponds to one spatial cluster. A directed edge $(v_i, v_j) \in E$ is created if, in at least one original trajectory in D , a GPS point assigned to cluster v_i is followed in the trajectory by a point assigned to cluster v_j . The weight $w_{ij} \in W$ is defined as the number of such observed transitions in the dataset. Therefore, heavily used transitions receive larger weights, while rare transitions receive smaller weights.

Finally, G provides a compact representation of the mobility patterns contained in D . This is important because instead of modeling trajectories directly in continuous geographic space, we abstract model movement as transitions over an abstract network of locations.

C. Synthetic trajectory generation

Given the mobility graph G , a synthetic trajectory is generated by the function $gen(\cdot)$ and consists of three steps. First, a source node v_s is sampled according to the empirical distribution of trajectory starting locations.

Second, we generate an abstract path starting from v_s by performing a biased random walk on G . As a baseline for trajectory generation, we adopt a second-order Markov random walk on the mobility graph, where the transition probabilities depend on the two previously visited locations. At each step, the next node is sampled from the outgoing neighbors of the current node with probability proportional to the corresponding edge weights. This biases the walk toward transitions that are more frequently observed in the data, while still preserving variability in the generated paths. To ensure comparability with real pedestrian mobility patterns, synthetic trajectory lengths are determined by randomly sampling the length of a trajectory from dataset D_1 , the high-resolution pedestrian dataset described in Section IV-A. This choice reflects the fact that D_1 more closely represents raw pedestrian movement, while trajectories in D_2 are span longer temporal intervals (see Section IV-A). The result of $gen(G)$ is an ordered sequence of clusters:

$$P = (v_s, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_T) \quad (3)$$

where the final node v_T denotes the arrival location reached after a finite number of random-walk steps. Since no destination is predefined, arrival locations emerge from the empirical transition structure encoded in the graph. Node revisits are allowed, while infinite loops are prevented by the finite sampled trajectory length.

Third, the abstract path is transformed into a realistic geographic trajectory. Each cluster node in the abstract sequence P is associated with a representative location, computed as the centroid of the cluster. For every consecutive pair of nodes in P , we compute a feasible pedestrian route between their representative locations using a routing engine on the road network. The routing is performed on a pedestrian graph derived from OpenStreetMap¹ data, ensuring that generated paths follow walkable streets and respect the urban infrastructure. Each abstract transition is resolved independently, and the resulting routed segments are concatenated in sequence. This produces a continuous trajectory in geographic coordinates that is physically plausible while preserving the higher-level movement structure defined by the mobility graph.

Finally, applying $gen(G)$ repeatedly produces a synthetic dataset of trajectories:

$$D_S = gen(G). \quad (4)$$

This procedure combines data-driven transition modeling with infrastructure-aware routing, ensuring that the generated trajectories remain statistically grounded in the original data while remaining physically plausible. The proposed approach is inherently modular, enabling flexible application across different datasets and domains.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Datasets

For our experiments, as described in Section I, we use two different and complementary datasets, described below (see Table I for details). For both datasets, before merging them, we filter only pedestrian trajectories by extracting only movements consistent with walking behaviour, identified using a maximum speed threshold of 4 km/h.

Dataset 1 (D_1) consists of 1,000 trajectories in the Paris area, covering about 18×10 km. It contains 110,310 GPS points collected between August 27 and September 30, 2023. The data comes from a commercial broker that aggregates

¹<https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

TABLE I: Statistics of the original trajectory datasets

Statistic	D_1	D_2
Total records	110,310	373,958
Number of traj.	1,000	581
Time span	27/8/2023 – 30/9/2023	1/1/2000 – 26/12/2024
Total duration	33 days 23:59:04	20,083 days 12:59:20
Mean traj. length	110.31	643.65
Median traj. length	81.50	431.00
Min traj. length	21	1
Max traj. length	1,618	10,168

anonymized signals from various mobile applications. Because of this, the sampling intervals are very irregular, with a median of 208.0 seconds and a high standard deviation ($\sigma = 1537.4s$). The average speed is 1.77 m/s ($\sigma = 4.08$ m/s), which reflects a mix of different transport modes typical for a dense urban environment.

In contrast, Dataset 2 (D_2), publicly available and detailed in [10], contains fewer trajectories (581), but spans a much longer temporal range, representing the entire user’s movement history. This results in significantly longer and more variable trajectory lengths.

In our work, we combine D_1 and D_2 to expose the clustering and graph abstraction to heterogeneous data regimes. This setting evaluates whether the proposed pipeline captures robust mobility structure rather than overfitting to the characteristics of a single data source. From now on, we call D the dataset resulting from the merge of D_1 and D_2 .

B. Evaluation metrics

In evaluating synthetic human mobility trajectories, the literature typically distinguishes between two categories of metrics: (i) statistical, distribution-based measures and (ii) trajectory-level similarity measures [11]. Statistical and distribution-based metrics assess how well population-level mobility patterns are preserved by comparing aggregated properties, such as trip lengths, stay durations, and visitation frequencies. In contrast, trajectory-level similarity measures quantify the similarity between individual trajectories using measures such as dynamic time warping (DTW), Fréchet distance, and longest common subsequence (LCSS), capturing fine-grained spatial and temporal correspondences [12].

In this work, we adopt the first category and focus exclusively on the spatial dimension, excluding temporal information from the evaluation. We deliberately avoid trajectory-level similarity measures, as they may favor close correspondence with individual paths and are less aligned with our goal of assessing distribution-level spatial fidelity.

To assess spatial fidelity, we compare the empirical spatial distributions of real and generated trajectories over a discretized grid. We partition the study region into K cells, and let p_i and q_i denote the normalized number of GPS points in cell i for the real and generated data, respectively. On the grid, we measure the following metrics:

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE)**. It measures the average squared difference between corresponding cell probabil-

TABLE II: Summary of graph metrics for different clustering approaches

Clustering	Nodes	Edges	Diam.	#Comp	Density	Avg. degree
Aggl-0.25	1098	6744	9	4	0.006	12.284
Aggl-0.5	609	5562	7	2	0.015	18.266
Aggl-1.0	328	4383	4	1	0.041	26.726
Aggl-2.0	178	3235	4	1	0.103	36.348
Aggl-3.0	119	2552	3	1	0.182	42.891
Aggl-5.0	73	1759	3	1	0.335	48.192
DBSCAN	248	1083	8	17	0.018	8.734

ities. It provides a simple pointwise assessment of how much the two distributions deviate locally. Lower values indicate better agreement.

- **Jensen–Shannon divergence (JSD)** [13], [14]. The JSD is a symmetric and bounded measure that quantifies differences between the two distributions. Intuitively, it compares each distribution to its average, providing a stable measure of similarity. Lower values indicate greater agreement between the real and synthetic spatial distribution.
- **Earth Mover’s Distance (EMD)** [15]. It measures the minimum effort required to transform one spatial distribution into the other by moving probability mass across the grid.
- **Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC)**. We compute PCC between the real and synthetic grid-cell densities. PCC evaluates whether dense and sparse areas are reproduced consistently across space, regardless of small local absolute differences. A value close to 1 indicates strong preservation of the original spatial pattern.

Taken together, these metrics provide complementary perspectives on fidelity: JSD and MSE quantify distribution similarity, EMD captures spatial fidelity by accounting for displacement across the grid, and PCC measures the preservation of the overall spatial structure between real and synthetic trajectories.

C. Results

In our evaluation, we first compare two clustering methods: agglomerative and DBSCAN clustering. As shown in the following results, agglomerative clustering achieves better performance. We therefore focus on this method and examine in detail how the distance threshold, d_{th} , affects the results. This parameter defines the maximum distance between clusters in the standardized spatial feature space and thus determines the characteristic spatial scale of the clustering, ranging from very local interactions to neighborhood-level aggregation.

1) *Agglomerative clustering vs DBSCAN*: First, as shown in Table II, we compare the networks generated by the various clustering approaches quantitatively. These structural properties directly affect trajectory generation. Dense, low-diameter graphs allow random walks to explore diverse paths while maintaining global connectivity, whereas fragmented graphs constrain walks to local components, increasing spatial bias and limiting coverage.

For agglomerative clustering, increasing the distance threshold (d_{th}) reduces the number of nodes while preserving a relatively large number of transitions (i.e., cluster-to-cluster movements), leading to higher density, higher average degree, smaller diameter, and fewer connected components. This indicates that coarser clustering produces a more compact and globally connected abstraction of movement. In contrast, DBSCAN yields a sparser and more fragmented graph, with fewer edges relative to its size and many disconnected components. These results suggest that agglomerative clustering appears to provide a more coherent network structure for trajectory generation, while DBSCAN tends to over-fragment the mobility space.

Figure 2 presents a qualitative comparison between the spatial density heatmaps of the original trajectories and the synthetic datasets generated using agglomerative clustering and DBSCAN. When using agglomerative clustering with distance threshold $d_{th} = 2$, the synthetic heatmap closely matches the original distribution, reproducing both major pedestrian hotspots and the smooth spatial gradients connecting them. This visual similarity suggests that the corresponding mobility graph is sufficiently dense and well connected to allow random walks to explore the urban area without introducing strong spatial bias. In contrast, the DBSCAN-based approach yields a visibly more fragmented heatmap, with activity concentrated in a limited number of disconnected regions and poor coverage of transitional areas. This reflects the fragmented structure of the underlying graph, which restricts random walks to small connected components and results in an uneven spatial distribution.

These qualitative observations are consistent with the quantitative results reported in Table III, where agglomerative clustering achieves lower divergence and higher spatial correlation with respect to the original data.

TABLE III: Summary of the trajectory datasets analyses. D_S stays for synthetic dataset and D for the merge of D_1 and D_2 .

Setup combination	MSE ↓	JSD ↓	EMD ↓	PCC ↑
D_S vs D , Aggl.	61.82	0.13617	0.02297	0.9465
D_S vs D , DBSCAN	142.28	0.18450	0.03055	0.8722

Across all evaluation criteria, agglomerative clustering shows higher agreement with the original data than DBSCAN. For both methods, the EMD values [15] are close to zero on a 0–1 scale, indicating strong overall similarity between generated and real trajectory densities; however, the lower EMD of the agglomerative model suggests a better reproduction of the overall spatial flow patterns. The lower JSD further indicates that agglomerative clustering more accurately captures the original trajectory distribution. Similarly, the higher MSE observed for DBSCAN reflects greater pointwise deviation from the original density field, while the lower MSE of the agglomerative model indicates better local spatial agreement. This is also supported by the higher PCC obtained with

agglomerative clustering, which indicates a more consistent reproduction of spatial density variations.

Overall, the agglomerative clustering model more faithfully reproduces both the global and local characteristics of the original pedestrian density field.

2) *Analyses of the pipeline under different agglomerative clustering parameters:* Here we further investigate how the agglomerative clustering key parameter, the distance threshold d_{th} , affects the generated trajectories.

In Table IV and Figure 3, we present the evaluation results for different distance threshold values. The distance threshold determines the maximum distance at which two clusters can be merged and thus controls the granularity of the resulting groups. Since clustering is performed on standardized spatial coordinates, d_{th} represents a relative spatial scale. In our dataset, one unit of d_{th} corresponds approximately to a spatial distance of about $50m$, computed from the characteristic spatial dispersion of the data. Accordingly, the evaluated thresholds $d_{th} \in (0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5)$ span spatial scales ranging from very local interactions ($\sim 10\text{--}25m$) to larger neighborhood-level aggregation ($\sim 100\text{--}250m$).

The results show that the effect of the distance threshold on trajectory quality is neither gradual nor linear. For small values ($d_{th} = 0.25$ and $d_{th} = 0.5$), clustering preserves fine spatial details, leading to relatively good agreement with the original distribution. However, this also produces larger and less compact mobility graphs, which can limit the efficiency of the random walk.

At intermediate values, particularly $d_{th} = 2$, the clustering begins to merge spatially close but semantically distinct movement patterns. This leads to less representative clusters and less meaningful transitions in the mobility graph, resulting in a degradation of all evaluation metrics.

For larger thresholds ($d_{th} = 3$ and $d_{th} = 5$), clustering becomes more consistent, producing smoother spatial regions and smaller, denser graphs. Although some detail is lost, this structure enables more effective random walks and improves agreement between real and synthetic distributions.

Overall, these findings indicate that intermediate clustering scales can be problematic, as they are too coarse to preserve local movement characteristics but not coarse enough to provide a stable and useful abstraction. In contrast, sufficiently fine or sufficiently coarse clustering configurations lead to more reliable synthetic trajectory generation.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper addresses the inherent tension between data utility and data confidentiality in synthetic mobility data generation. We introduce a graph-based approach that combines spatial clustering, transition modeling, and random walk sampling to produce trajectories that preserve global mobility patterns while potentially reducing individual-level similarity. We explicitly control the level of abstraction in the generated data, enabling a systematic investigation of its impact on trajectory realism and generalization. We evaluate on two complementary datasets that differ in scale, richness, and

Fig. 2: Comparison of original and generated trajectories heatmaps

TABLE IV: Analyses of the pipeline under different agglomerative clustering parameters.

Distance threshold	MSE ↓	JSD ↓	EMD ↓	PCC ↑
$d_{th}=0.25$	78.60	0.13581	0.02406	0.9397
$d_{th}=0.5$	85.19	0.13435	0.02723	0.923
$d_{th}=1.0$	98.13	0.14016	0.02788	0.92
$d_{th}=2.0$	106.56	0.14654	0.03045	0.9185
$d_{th}=3.0$	93.85	0.14216	0.02742	0.9244
$d_{th}=5.0$	92.97	0.1507	0.02782	0.9286

Fig. 3: Evaluation metrics comparing real and generated trajectory datasets across agglomerative clustering distance thresholds d_{th} . Each subfigure captures a distinct aspect of similarity.

sensitivity, providing a comprehensive testbed for assessing performance across heterogeneous trajectory sampling. This approach is inherently interpretable and modular, making it suitable for different datasets and domains. As future work,

we intend to introduce the temporal aspect into the graph representation and the trajectory generation. We plan to explore other graph reconstruction techniques and extend them to other domains, like the AIS vessels data in the maritime domain.

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